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Comparative Adsorption Mechanism of Musa Sapientum Peels Extracts for Green Corrosion Inhibition of Mild Steel in Sulphuric Acid

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Comparative Adsorption Mechanism of Musa Sapientum Peels Extracts for Green Corrosion Inhibition of Mild Steel in Sulphuric Acid

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ABSTRACT

The production of green corrosion inhibitors from locally sourced organic wastes makes environmental friendly corrosion inhibitor available. The aim and objective of this is to produce corrosion inhibitor from local Musa Sapientum Peels with a perspective of establishing the kinetics of the adsorption of Musa Sapientum Peels extract on mild steel bar in 2.0M sulphuric acid. Musa Sapientum Peels extract produced was used as a corrosion inhibitor on mild steel bar in concentrated sulphuric acid using weight loss method. The results showed that the concentration of corrosion inhibitor is directly proportional to inhibitor efficiency and surface coverage but inversely proportional to weight loss of mild steel bar. Langmuir Isotherm, Freundlich Isotherm and Kinetic – Thermodynamic model predicted the kinetics of the ethanol extract of Musa Sapientum peels used as a corrosion inhibitor of mild steel bar while Linear isotherm did not. Among the three isotherms that predicted the results, Freundlich has the best correlation than Langmuir and Kinetic – Thermodynamic model based on the value of the goodness fit.

Keywords: adsorption, corrosion inhibitor, musa sapientum, mild steel, sulphuric acid.

INTRODUCTION

Corrosion which is the gradual destruction of materials, usually metals, by chemical reactions is a serious engineering problem in this modern era of the technology advancement (Sudhish et al., 2011). An enormous breadth of engineering systems depends upon corrosion protection for their reliability, performance and safety (Obot et al., 2009). The corrosion of metallic materials in acidic solution causes considerable costs. The cost of corrosion study estimated that in 2002, corrosion drained about 3.1% of the gross domestic product (GDP) from the US economy. On this basis, the direct economic loss from corrosion is US in 2004 was put at \$364 billion (Rapp, 2006). In this sense, corrosion is the largest continuing technical calamity of our time. As a result, corrosion prevention is very important especially in the industries.

The use of inhibitors is one of the best options of protecting metals against corrosion. Several inhibitors in use are either synthesized from cheap raw materials or chosen from compounds having hetero atoms in their aromatic or long chain carbon system which allows adsorption on the metal surface (Eddy and Ebenso, 2008; Fekry and Ameer, 2010 and Abboud et al., 2009). To be effective, an inhibitor must displace water from the metal surface, interact with anodic or cathodic reaction sites to retard the oxidation, reduce corrosion reaction and prevent transportation of water and corrosion active species on the surface (Obot et al., 2011). Inhibitors which reduce corrosion on metallic materials, can be divided into three kinds: (i) inorganic inhibitors (ii) organic inhibitors and (iii) mixed material inhibitor (Ebenso et al., 2008). However, in the use of these inhibitors for corrosion control, factors such as cost, toxicity, availability and environmental friendliness are very important (Obot et al., 2011). Most inhibitors presently use in the industries today are toxic (Eddy and Ebenso, 2008) and this has prompted the search for green corrosion inhibitors.

Green corrosion inhibitors are biodegradable and do not contain heavy metals or other toxic compounds. There has been a growing interest in the use of organic compounds as inhibitors for the corrosion of metals. Inhibitors can adhere to a material surface to form a protective barrier against corrosive agents in contact with the metal. The effectiveness of an inhibitor to provide corrosion protection depends to a larger extent on the interaction between the inhibitor and the metal surface (Ebenso et al., 2010). The adsorbed inhibitors can affect the corrosion reaction, either by the blocking effect of the adsorbed inhibitor on the metal surface or by the effects attributed to the change in activation barrier of the anodic and cathodic reactions of the corrosion process (Ebenso et al., 2010). This work was designed as a contribution to the growing interest on environmentally benign corrosion inhibitors. The aim and objective of this work is to produce corrosion inhibitor from local banana

(Musa Sapiantum) peel with a perspective of establishing the kinetics of the adsorption of Musa Sapiantum extract on mild steel bar in 2.0M H₂SO₄ .

Adsorption Considerations

Adsorption depends mainly on the charge and nature of the metal surface, electronic characteristics of the metal surface, adsorption of solvent and other ionic species, temperature of corrosion reaction and on the electrochemical potential at solution – interface (Obot et al., 2009 and Rozendeld, 1981). Adsorption of inhibitor involves the formation of two types of interaction responsible for bonding of inhibitor to a metal surface. The first one (physical adsorption) is weak undirected interaction and is due to electrostatic attraction between inhibiting organic ions or dipoles and the electrostatic adsorption process. The second type of interaction (adsorption) occurs when directed forces govern the interaction between the adsorbate and adsorbent. Chemical adsorption involves charge sharing or charge transfer from adsorbates to the metal surface atoms in order to form a coordinate type of bond. Chemical adsorption has a free energy of adsorption and activation energy higher than physical adsorption and hence, usually it is irreversible (Obot et al., 2009 and Trabanelli, 1987)

Adsorption isotherms are very important in understanding the mechanism of inhibition of corrosion reactions. Adsorption isotherms provide information about the interaction among adsorbed molecules themselves as well as their interactions with the metal surface (Obot et al., 2011). Corrosion mechanism can vary considerably depending on the corrosive factors that are present. Similarly, the mechanism of inhibition will vary depending on the chemical nature of the inhibitor and the factor causing corrosion (Sastri, 2001). The most widely accepted postulate involves the formation of surface layers or films which reduce the ease of access of the corrosive materials to the metal surface. Such scale can be formed naturally or can be induced to form the scale (Obot et al., 2009). An equation which relates the amount of substance attached to surface, to its concentration in gas phase or in solution at fixed temperature is known as an adsorption isotherm.

Langmuir Isotherm

The simplest isotherm was first obtained in 1916 by Irvan Langmuir (El-Egamy, 2008). This isotherm is represented as:

$$\theta = \frac{KC}{1+KC} \quad (1)$$

Where K is the equilibrium constant

C is the inhibitor concentration

θ is the surface coverage

The equation (1) was derived based on the following assumptions:

- The adsorbed entities (atoms, molecules or ions) are attached to the surface at definite localized sites.
- Each site accommodates one and only one adsorbed entity
- The energy state of each adsorbed entity is the same at all sites on the surface independent of the presence or absence of other adsorbed entities at neighbouring sites
- The surface is perfectly smooth and homogenous and that the lateral interactions between the adsorbed entities are negligible.

Systems that obey equation (1) are often referred to ideal adsorption Systems frequently deviate significantly from Langmuir equation. This may be attributed to surface not uniform and also there may be interaction between adsorbed molecules, a molecule attached to surface may make it more difficult or less difficult, for another molecules to become attached to a neighbouring site and this will lead to deviation from the ideal adsorption equation [Obot et al., 2009]

Rearranging equation (1) gives:

$$\frac{1}{\theta} = \frac{1+KC}{KC} \quad (2)$$

Multiplying both side by C yields :

$$\frac{C}{\theta} = \frac{1}{K} + C \quad (3)$$

Linearising equation (3) gives :

$$\ln\left(\frac{C}{\theta}\right) = \ln C - \ln K \quad (4)$$

Moreover, the essential characteristics of the Langmuir Isotherm can be expressed in terms of a dimensionless separation factor R_L (Unuabonah et al.,2007) which describes the type of isotherm and defined by:

$$R_L = \frac{1}{1 + KC} \quad (5)$$

Table 1 shows the type of isotherm and respective R_L values

Table 1: Types of Isotherm and R_L values

Values of R_L	Type of Isotherm
$R_L > 1$	Unfavourable
$R_L = 1$	Linear
$0 < R_L < 1$	Favourable
$R_L = 0$	Irreversible

Freundlich Isotherm

Non – ideal system can sometimes be fitted to an empirical adsorption isotherm of Freundlich represented by:

$$\theta = KC^N \quad (6)$$

The Freundlich isotherm theory says that the ratio of the amount of solute adsorbed onto a given mass of sorbent to the concentration of the solute in the solution is not constant at different concentration (Unuabonah et al.,2007).

Linearising equation (6), we have:

$$\ln\theta = \ln K + N \ln C \quad (7)$$

Where N is the Freundlich isotherm constant

Kinetic – Thermodynamic

A kinetic – thermodynamic model for adsorption process at metal – solution interface has been suggested (Obot et al., 2009).The El-Awady Kinetic – thermodynamic model can be represented by equation (8).

$$\frac{\theta}{1-\theta} = K' C^y \quad (8)$$

Linearising equation (8), we have

$$\text{Ln}\left(\frac{\theta}{1-\theta}\right) = \text{Ln}K' + y\text{Ln}C \quad (9)$$

Where y is the Kinetic–thermodynamic isotherm constant.

If a value of y is greater than 1, it means the formation of multilayer of inhibitor on the surface of metal. If values of y is less than 1, a given inhibitor molecules will occupy more than one active site.

$$K = K' \left(\frac{1}{y}\right) \quad (10)$$

Linear Isotherm

The simplest relationship between solid phase and fluid phase is the linear isotherm. At very low concentrations the molecules adsorbed are widely spaced over the adsorbent surface so that one molecule has no influence on another. For these limiting conditions, it is reasonable to assume that the concentration in one phase is proportional to the concentration in the other phase (Jinadu, 2010). In terms of surface coverage and concentration, linear isotherm is described in equation (11).

$$\theta = KC \quad (11)$$

Linearizing equation (11), it yields:

$$\text{Ln}\theta = \text{Ln}K + \text{Ln}C \quad (12)$$

A plot of $\text{Ln}\theta$ against $\text{Ln}C$ will give a straight line with slope of one, having intercept at y -axis

Experimental

Materials Preparation

Mild steel bar of composition (wt%) Mn (0.6), P(0.36), C(0.15), Si(0.03) and the rest Fe was used for the study. Five mild steel bars each of weight 35.50g were mechanically cut and washed with ethanol to remove any form of grease or oxide. The bars were then dried in acetone and preserved in a desiccator to prevent a reaction with the environment or the formation of a passivation layer which might interfere with the results of the experiment. All reagents used in this study were analytical grade.

Musa Sapientum Extract

2kg of fresh samples of Musa Sapientum peels were collected from Ayetoro market in Epe area of Lagos State and were washed carefully with distill water to remove any form of dirt from the peels. The peels were dried under the sun and weighed at intervals until a constant weight of 1.20kg was attained. This was to ensure complete removal of water from the peels. The dried Musa Sapientum peels were grounded using an industrial scale grinder to powdered form. The powdered Musa Sapientum peels was then run through wire mesh sifter to obtain very fine powdered samples and to separate the shaft of the peels. The fine powdered peels were completely soaked in ethanol solution for 96hours after which the mixture was stirred properly in order to have homogenous solution and then filtered. The filtrate was subjected to evaporation process to remove the ethanol in the filtrate. The inhibitor was obtained in its pure form at the end of the evaporation process. The stock solution of the extract obtained were used in preparing different concentrations of the extract by dissolving 0.2, 0.4, 0.6 and 0.8g of the extract in 1 litre of 2.0M H_2SO_4 respectively.

Weight Loss Method

One of the mild steel bars was inserted in 2.0M H_2SO_4 without Musa Sapientum extract (Og/L) and then removed and weighed at 120hrs to determine loss of weight. It was ensured all inhibitor solution dropped from the bar before weighing measurement was carried out. The same procedure was carried out for 0.2g/l, 0.4g/l, 0.6g/l and 0.8g/l of 2.0M H_2SO_4 . All experiments performed were at ambient temperature.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Table 2: Weight Loss of steel bar in different concentration of Musa Sapientum extract in 2.0 M H₂SO₄ and the inhibition efficiency as well as surface coverage.

Concentration of Musa Sapientum extract in 2.0 MH ₂ SO ₄ (g/l)	Weight of bar loss (g)	%IE	θ
0.00	0.34	0.00	0.00
0.20	0.25	26.47	0.26
0.40	0.20	41.18	0.41
0.60	0.14	58.82	0.59
0.80	0.10	70.59	0.71

Table 3: Values for plotting equilibrium isotherms

C (g/l)	θ	LnC (g/l)	$\frac{C}{\theta}$ (g/l)	$Ln\left(\frac{C}{\theta}\right)$ (g/l)	Ln θ	$\frac{\theta}{1-\theta}$	$Ln\left(\frac{\theta}{1-\theta}\right)$
0.00	0.00	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.20	0.26	- 1.609	0.7692	- 0.2624	- 1.3470	0.3514	- 1.046
0.40	0.41	- 0.916	0.9756	- 0.0247	- 0.8916	0.6949	- 0.364
0.60	0.59	- 0.5108	1.017	0.019	- 0.5276	1.4390	0.3639
0.80	0.71	- 0.2231	1.127	0.120	- 0.3425	2.4483	0.8954

Table 4: Equilibrium Isotherm parameters by linear method

Isotherm	Parameters	Values
Langmuir	K	1.2337
	R ²	0.9701
Freundlich	N	0.7358
	K	0.206
	R ²	0.9958
Kinetic – Thermodynamic	K ¹	0.2276
	K	0.3452
	Y	1.3918
	R ²	0.9739
Linear	K	0.206
	R ²	0.9958
	Slope	0.7358

Table 5: R_L values for different concentrations of corrosion inhibitor and their type of isotherm

Concentration of Musa Sapientum extract in 2.0MH ₂ SO ₄ (g/l)	R _L Value	Type of Isotherm
0.00	1	Linear
0.20	0.8021	Favourable
0.40	0.6696	Favourable
0.60	0.5775	Favourable
0.80	0.5033	Favourable

Table 6: Experimental and Simulated as well as percentage error values for Langmuir and Freundlich Isotherm model.

Concentration of Musa Sapiantum extract in 2.0M H ₂ SO ₄ (g/l)	θ expt.	θ simulated Langmuir	% error Langmuir	θ simulated Freundlich	% error Freundlich
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.20	0.26	0.20	23.08	0.06	76.92
0.40	0.41	0.33	19.51	0.11	73.17
0.60	0.59	0.43	27.12	0.14	76.27
0.80	0.71	0.50	29.58	0.17	76.06

Table 7: Experimental and Simulated as well as percentage error for Kinetic – Thermodynamic and Linear Isotherm Model

Concentration of Musa Sapiantum extract in 2.0MH ₂ SO ₄ (g/l)	θ expt.	θ Simulated Kinetic-Thermodynamic	% error Kinetic – Thermodynamic	θ Simulated Linear	% error Linear
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.20	0.26	0.02	92.30	0.04	84.15
0.40	0.41	0.06	85.37	0.08	79.90
0.60	0.59	0.10	83.05	0.12	79.05
0.80	0.71	0.14	80.28	0.16	76.79

Table 8: Values of Experimental and Simulated Surface Coverage as well as Concentration of Extract.

Concentration of Musa Sapiantum extract in 2.0MH ₂ SO ₄ (g/l)	θ expt.	θ Simulated Langmuir	θ Simulated Freundlich	θ Simulated Kinetic Thermodynamic	θ Simulated Linear
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.20	0.26	0.20	0.06	0.02	0.041
0.40	0.41	0.33	0.11	0.06	0.08
0.60	0.59	0.43	0.14	0.10	0.12
0.80	0.71	0.50	0.17	0.14	0.16

Fig 1: Langmuir Adsorption Isotherm Plot

Fig 2: Freundlich Adsorption Isotherm Plot

Fig 3: Kinetic – Thermodynamic Model Plot

Fig 4: Linear Adsorption Isotherm Plot

DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the weight loss of steel bar in different concentration of *Musa Sapientum* extract in 2.0M H_2SO_4 and the inhibition efficiency as well as surface coverage. It revealed that as the concentration of inhibitor increases, the weight of mild steel bar loss decreases. This means that the inhibitor concentration is inversely proportional to weight loss of materials. This supports the findings of previous works (Eddy and Ebenso, 2008; Ebenso, and Ekpe, 1996; Ebenso, E. E., Ekpe and Ibok, 1998; El-Etre and Abdallah, 2000; Ekpe et al., 1994; Kliskic et al., 2000; Choy, 1999; Guptha et al., 2007; Okuonrobo et al., 2011 and Zucchi and Omar, 1985). Table 2 also revealed that as the inhibitor concentration increases, percentage inhibitor efficiency also increases which means inhibitor efficiency is directly proportional to inhibitor concentration. Table 2 was used to generate Table 3. Table 4 shows the equilibrium isotherms parameters obtained by linear method and with the plots of Figure 1 to 4 while Table 5 revealed that the R_L values are favourable except for blank concentration which is linear.

Figures 1 to 4 show the Langmuir adsorption isotherm plot, Freundlich adsorption isotherm plot, Kinetic – Thermodynamic model plot and linear adsorption isotherm plot respectively. The value of equilibrium constant, K , obtained from Figure 1 was put in equation 2 which was used to generate surface coverage simulated Langmuir, ($\theta_{\text{simulated Langmuir}}$) shown in Table 6. The value of equilibrium constant and Freundlich isotherm constant (N) obtained from Figure 2 were put in equation 6 which was used to generate surface coverage simulated Freundlich ($\theta_{\text{simulated Freundlich}}$) shown also in Table 6. The percentage errors for Langmuir and Freundlich are also presented in Table 6.

The value of equilibrium constant and Kinetic – Thermodynamic isotherm constant (y) obtained from Figure 3 were inserted in equation 8 which forms the Kinetic – Thermodynamic model. This model was used to generate surface coverage simulated Thermodynamic shown in Table 7. In Figure 4, the equilibrium constant obtained was put in equation 11, which was then used to generate surface coverage simulated linear also shown in Table 7. The percentage errors for Kinetic – Thermodynamic model and linear adsorption isotherm are also presented in Table 7. Table 8 was extracted from Table 6 and 7. It was observed that as the concentration of extract increases, the surface coverage for both experimental and simulated isotherm increases. This means that concentration of extract is directly proportional to experimental and simulated isotherm.

The prediction by Langmuir isotherm showed that the adsorbed atoms and molecules of the ethanol extract are attached to the surface of the mild steel bar at definite localized site and each site accommodates one and only one adsorbed atoms or molecules of the ethanol extract. It also showed that the surface of the mild steel bar is perfectly smooth and homogenous and that the lateral interactions between the adsorbed molecules are negligible. Moreover, the energy state of each adsorbed ethanol extract is the same at all sites on the surface

independent of the presence or absence of other adsorbed molecules at neighbouring sites. The prediction of Kinetic – Thermodynamic model showed the formation of multilayer of the inhibitor on the surface of the mild steel bar since the Kinetic – Thermodynamic isotherm constant is greater than one. However, the non prediction of linear isotherm does not support the assumption that the concentration in one phase is proportional to the concentration in other phase at very low concentration.

CONCLUSION

The results of this work have shown that *Musa Sapientum* extract can be used as corrosion inhibitor. Four adsorption isotherms were considered in this work out of which three predicted the kinetics of ethanol extract of *Musa Sapientum* on mild steel bar. The adsorption isotherms that predicted the kinetic are Langmuir, Freundlich, and Kinetic – Thermodynamic model while Linear isotherm did not. Among the three isotherms that predicted the results, Freundlich has the best correlation than Langmuir and Kinetic – Thermodynamic model based on the value of the goodness fit.

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